

Studies in Catalytic Dehydrogenation. Part VIII. Synthesis and Dehydrogenation of Spiro-[6,5]dodecanes

S. C. Sen Gupta and Parimal Krishna Sen

Syntheses of 8,9-benzo-spiro-(6,5) dodecene and its alkyl derivatives have been described. Dehydrogenation of these spirans accompanied by ring transformation occurs when heated with Pd-C at 370-400° in a sealed tube, providing an anthracene or a phenanthrene derivative as the main product.

We had described in a previous communication¹ in this series the syntheses and catalytic dehydrogenation of several spiro-(6,4)undecanes. We have now synthesised several spiro-(6,5)dodecanes, that is, spirans with a seven-carbon ring system and a six-carbon ring system having a common carbon atom, with a view to studying the catalytic dehydrogenation of these compounds. In these cases also, these spirans have been found not to be affected when heated with Pd-C catalyst at 350° in a metal-bath, but dehydrogenation accompanied by ring transformation occurs only when heated with Pd-C in a sealed tube at 380-400°. Under this condition 8,9-benzo-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (IV: R₁=R₂=H) gave anthracene as the main dehydrogenation product along with traces of *o*-xylene. 3'-Methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(6,5) dodecane (IV: R₁=Me; R₂=H) gave on dehydrogenation mainly 2-methylanthracene and a small amount of 1,2,4-trimethylbenzene. 3'-Ethyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(6,5) dodecane (IV: R₁=Et; R₂=H) gave 2-ethylanthracene as the only dehydrogenation product. It has, however, been found that 3-methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (IV: R₁=H; R₂=Me) gave 3-methylphenanthrene and *o*-xylene as the dehydrogenation products; no anthracene derivative could be detected. During dehydrogenation, contraction of the seven-carbon ring system in all these cases took place along with the rearrangement of the cyclohexane ring, giving ultimately anthracene or phenanthrene derivative, with a loss of two carbon atoms.

1. Sen Gupta and Sen, *the Journal* 1962, 39, 660.

The following steps may possibly interpret the course of the dehydrogenation reaction. The seven-carbon ring in the spiran (V) first opens up with the formation of an intermediate (VI) which then ring-closes with the formation of an intermediate naphthalene derivative (VII) containing an angular methyl group and a cyclohexane ring in spiran formation. The cyclohexane ring in this intermediate spiran next opens up and then ring-closes either in a linear or in an angular manner (VIII) or (IX) with the formation of an anthracene or a phenanthrene derivative with two angular methyl groups, which are lost during aromatisation, giving ultimately an anthracene or a phenanthrene derivative.

The fact that 3-methylphenanthrene is formed as the main dehydrogenation product of 3-methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (IV : $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Me$) to the exclusion of an anthracene derivative makes it evident that during dehydrogenation the intermediate (VII) opens along the dotted lines and then ring-closes in an angular manner, furnishing ultimately 3-methylphenanthrene. In all the three other cases, where there is no alkyl substituent in the spiro-(6,5)dodecane ring system, anthracene derivatives have been obtained as the dehydrogenation product and no phenanthrene.

The formation of a small amount of *o*-xylene or 1,2,4-trimethylbenzene as dehydrogenation products can be explained by assuming that the seven-carbon ring system in the spiran also opens along with the dotted lines, as shown in (V).

The four spiro-hydrocarbons required for dehydrogenation experiments have been synthesised from substituted δ -arylvaleric acids by an extension of the method we had followed earlier for the synthesis of 7,8-benzo-spiro-(6,4)undecanes'. For the synthesis of 8,9-benzo-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (IV: $R_1=R_2=H$), anhydride of cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic acid was condensed with benzene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, yielding $\beta\beta$ -cyclohexane- γ -benzoylbutyric acid (I: $R_1=R_2=H$). The keto-acid on the Clemmensen reduction gave $\beta\beta$ -cyclohexane- δ -phenylvaleric acid (II: $R_1=R_2=H$), which was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid, yielding 8,9-benzo-10-keto-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (III: $R_1=R_2=H$). The spiro-ketone on the Clemmensen reduction gave 8,9-benzo-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (IV: $R_1=R_2=H$).

In a similar manner, 3'-methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(6,5) dodecane (IV: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$) and 3'-ethyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (IV: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$) have been synthesised from toluene and anhydride of cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic acid and from ethylbenzene and anhydride of cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic acid respectively. Formation of terephthalic acid by alkaline permanganate oxidation of the keto-acids (I: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$) and (I: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$) gave a definite proof that the Friedel-Crafts reaction took place at the *para* position to the alkyl group present in the aromatic ring. 3-Methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (IV: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$) has been synthesised similarly starting from benzene and anhydride of 4-methylcyclohexane-1,1-diacetic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

$\beta\beta$ -Cyclohexane- γ -benzoylbutyric acid (I: $R_1=R_2=H$) and $\beta\beta$ -cyclohexane- δ -phenylvaleric acid (II: $R_1=R_2=H$) were prepared according to Ali *et al.*². The reduced acid was purified by distillation, b.p. 188°/1 mm. The heavy viscous oil soon solidified and was crystallised from hexane, m.p. 57-58°.

8,9-Benzo-spiran (IV: $R_1=R_2=H$)

8,9-Benzo-10-keto-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (III: $R_1=R_2=H$).—The valeric acid (II: $R_1=R_2=H$) (10 g.) and polyphosphoric acid (P_2O_5 , 60 g., 89% H_3PO_4 , 60ml) was heated on the steam bath for 1½ hrs. with stirring. The product was poured on crushed ice and the spiro-ketone was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with ammonia and then with water, dried with sodium sulphate, solvent removed, and the spiro-ketone distilled at 166-68°/1mm as a light straw-coloured liquid, which soon solidified. It was crystallised from hexane, m.p. 58°, yield 6.5 g. (Found: C, 84.35; H, 8.62. $C_{16}H_{20}O$ requires C, 84.21; H, 8.77%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 226°. (Found: C, 64.45; H, 5.58; N, 13.63. $C_{22}H_{24}O_4N_4$ requires C, 64.70; H, 5.88; N, 13.72 %).

8,9-Benzo-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (IV: $R_1=R_2=H$).—The spiro-ketone (III: $R_1=R_2=H$) (9 g.) was gently boiled with amalgamated zinc (40 g.) and HCl (conc., 40ml) for 24 hours. The product was extracted with ether, dried with sodium sulphate, and distilled, b.p.

2. Ali *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1013.

152-53°/1 mm, yield 6 g. It is a fragrant colorless liquid; d_4^{20} 0.9986, n_D^{20} 1.5445, $[R_1]_D$ 67.68 (calc. 68.252). (Found: C, 89.53; H, 10.24. $C_{16}H_{22}$ requires C, 89.71; H, 10.28%).

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of the Spiro-hydrocarbon (IV: R₁=R₂=H).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (2.51 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.28 g.) in a sealed pyrex tube at 380-400° for 18 hours. The product was extracted with ether, the solvent removed, and the residual oil was subjected to chromatographic fractionation on Brockmann alumina. Eluates (each 10 ml) were collected. The first and second eluates left after removal of the solvent an oily residue with the odour of xylene. The residues were mixed together and had b.p. 140-45°. The distillate was oxidised by alkaline permanganate solution when phthalic acid, m.p. 200° (decomp.), was obtained. The anhydride of the acid had m.p. 130°.

After removal of the solvent, each of the third and fourth eluates gave a small quantity of a solid. Trinitrobenzene derivative was prepared separately with the solids. They melted within the range of 155-60°. T.N.B. derivatives were mixed together and crystallised repeatedly from rectified spirit when orange-coloured needles melting at 161° were obtained. The mixed m.p. with the T.N.B. derivative of an authentic sample of anthracene was not depressed. (Found: C, 61.1; H, 3.24. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{13}O_6N_3$: C, 61.35; H, 3.32%).

The hydrocarbon was regenerated from T.N.B. derivative by passing benzene solution through Brockmann alumina and eluting with petroleum ether; it was crystallised from ethanol in colorless flakes, m.p. 216°. The mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of anthracene remained unaltered. (Found: C, 94.16; H, 5.8. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{10}$: C, 94.38; H, 5.61%).

8,9-Benzo-spiran (IV: R₁=Me; R₂=H)

ββ-Cyclohexane-γ-(p-toluy)butyric acid (I: R₁=Me; R₂=H) was prepared from anhydride of cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic acid (14 g.), toluene (70 ml), and aluminum chloride (27 g.) exactly as in the case of the keto-acid (I: R₁=R₂=H). It was crystallised from ethanol. After recrystallisation from hexane it melted at 87-88°; yield 21 g. (Found: C, 74.38; H, 8.3. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 74.45; H, 8.02%).

The semicarbazone crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 200° (decomp.). (Found: C, 65.42; H, 7.45; N, 12.52. $C_{18}H_{25}O_3N_3$ requires C, 65.25; H, 7.55; N, 12.68%).

Oxidation of the Keto-acid (I: R₁=Me; R₂=H).—The keto-acid was oxidised by heating with alkaline permanganate solution. The oxidation product was crystallised from HCl (conc.). The acid was characterised as terephthalic acid. It gave methyl ester, m.p. 140°.

ββ-Cyclohexane-δ-(p-tolyl)valeric Acid (II: R₁=Me; R₂=H).—The butyric acid (I: R₁=Me; R₂=H) (25 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (100 g.) and HCl (conc., 100 ml) for 24 hours. The reduced acid had b.p. 192-94°/1 mm, yield 12 g. (Found: C, 78.23; H, 9.51. $C_{17}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 78.46; H, 9.23%).

3'-Methyl-8,9-benzo-10-keto-spiro-(6,5) dodecane (III: R₁=Me; R₂=H).—The valeric acid (II: R₁=Me; R₂=H) (8 g.) was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid (P_2O_5 , 60 g., 89%)

H_3PO_4 , 40 ml) as in the preparation of the spiro-ketone (III: $R_1=H$; $R_2=H$). It is a light straw-coloured liquid, b.p. $178^\circ/1\text{mm}$. It gradually crystallised; m.p. $60-61^\circ$. (Found: C, 74.42; H, 9.2. $C_{17}H_{22}O$ requires C, 84.29; H, 9.09%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of the spiro-ketone crystallised from ethyl acetate as reddish needles, m.p. $216-17^\circ$. (Found: C, 65.28; H, 6.3; N, 13.0. $C_{23}H_{26}O_4N_4$ requires C, 65.40; H, 6.16; N, 13.27%).

3'-Methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(8,5)dodecane (IV: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$).—The spiro-ketone (III: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$) (6 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (30 g.) and HCl (conc., 30 ml) for 24 hours. It is colorless oil, b.p. $173-75^\circ/1\text{ mm}$, yield 4 g.; d_4^{32} 1.0, n_D^{32} 1.543, $[R_1]_D$ 71.87 (calc. 72.90). (Found: C, 89.18; H, 10.64. $C_{17}H_{24}$ requires C, 89.47; H, 10.52%).

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of the Spiro-hydrocarbon (IV: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (1.77 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.2 g.) in a sealed pyrex tube at $380-400^\circ$ for 16 hours. The product was subjected to chromatographic fractionation on Brockmann alumina with hexane as in the previous case. The first and the second eluates contained oily residues with characteristic odour. The oils did not form any T.N.B. complex. These were mixed together and distilled. The distillate was oxidised by an alkaline permanganate solution. The product was isolated and identified as trimellitic acid, m.p. 216° (decomp.).

On removal of the solvent, the third and the fourth eluates, each, left a small amount of a solid. Trinitrobenzene complex was prepared separately with the solid residues. These melted within range of $124^\circ-130^\circ$. T.N.B. derivatives were mixed together and crystallised repeatedly from rectified spirit when red needles, m.p. 130° , were obtained. The mixed melting point with the T.N.B. derivative of an authentic sample of 2-methylanthracene was not depressed. (Found: C, 61.89; H, 3.62. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{15}O_6N_3$: C, 62.22; H, 3.70%).

The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the T.N.B. derivative and crystallised from ethanol as colorless flakes, m.p. 201° ; the mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of 2-methylanthracene remained unaltered. (Found: C, 93.49; H, 6.23. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{15}$: C, 93.75; H, 6.25%).

8,9-Benzo-spiran (IV: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$)

β -Cyclohexane- δ -(p-ethylbenzoyl)butyric Acid (I: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$).—A solution of anhydride of cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic acid (15 g.) in ethylbenzene (20 ml) was added to an ice-cold suspension of anhydrous aluminium chloride (25 g.) in dry sym.-tetrachloroethane (75 ml). The product was purified as in the previous cases. It is a viscous liquid, b.p. $210-12^\circ/0.8\text{ mm}$, yield 10 g. (Found: C, 74.78; H, 8.23. $C_{18}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 8.33%).

The semicarbazone was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. $182-83^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: C, 65.82; H, 7.65; N, 12.32. $C_{16}H_{27}O_3N_3$ requires C, 66.08; H, 7.82; N, 12.17%).

Oxidation of the Keto-acid (I: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$).—The keto-acid was oxidised with an alkaline permanganate solution. The oxidation product was crystallised from HCl (conc.). The acid was characterised as terephthalic acid. It gave methyl ester, m.p. 140° .

$\beta\beta$ -Cyclohexane- δ -(*p*-ethylphenyl)valeric Acid (II: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$).—The butyric acid (I: $R=Et$; $R_2=H$) (55 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (200 g.) and HCl (conc., 200 ml) for 30 hours. The reduced acid had b.p. $210^\circ/1$ mm, yield 38 g. (Found: C 78.62; H, 9.42. $C_{18}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 78.83; H 9.48%).

3'-Ethyl-8,9-benzo-10-keto-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (III: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$).—The valeric acid (II: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$) (8.1 g.) was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid (P_2O_5 , 35 g., 89% H_2PO_4 , 15 ml) as in the preparation of the previous spiro ketones. It is a light straw-coloured liquid, b.p., $185-87^\circ/1$ mm, yield 4.19 g. (Found: C, 84.1; H, 9.26. $C_{18}H_{24}O$ requires C, 84.37; H, 9.37%).

The semicarbazone of the spiro-ketone crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 222° (decomp.). (Found: C, 72.45; H, 8.43; N, 13.8. $C_{19}H_{27}ON_3$ requires C, 72.86; H, 8.62; N, 13.41%).

3'-Ethyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (IV: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$).—The spiro-ketone (III: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$) (10 g.) was reduced with amalgamated zinc (40 g.) and HCl (conc., 40 ml) for 30 hours. It is a colorless oil, b.p. $165-67^\circ/1$ mm, yield 7 g.; d_4^{25} 0.9947, n_D^{25} 1.541, $[R_L]_D$ 76.45 (calc. 77.548). (Found: C, 89.16; H, 10.84. $C_{18}H_{26}$ requires C, 89.25; H, 10.74%).

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of the Spiro-hydrocarbon (IV: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (2.45 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.25 g.) in a sealed tube at $380-400^\circ$ for 16 hours. The product was subjected to chromatographic fractionation on Brockmann alumina with hexane as in the previous cases. The first and second eluates contained traces of unaltered spiro-hydrocarbon. The third and the fourth eluates gave pale yellow oil after removal of the solvent. The latter eluates did not contain any residue. Oils obtained in third and fourth eluates were separately converted into trinitrobenzene complex in ethanolic solution. They melted in the range between 110° and 118° . The T.N.B. derivatives were mixed together and crystallised repeatedly from ethanol when red needles melting at $119-20^\circ$ were obtained. (Found: C, 72.80; H, 4.08. $C_{22}H_{17}O_6N_3$ requires C, 63.0; H, 4.05%).

The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the T.N.B. derivative; it melted at $150-51^\circ$. Walmann and Marmorstein³ give the melting point of 2-ethylanthracene as $150-51^\circ$.

8,9-Benzo-spiran ($R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$)

$\beta\beta$ -(4'-Methylcyclohexane)- γ -benzoylbutyric acid (I: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$) was prepared from anhydride of 4-methylcyclohexane-1,1-diacetic acid (48 g.), dry benzene (150 ml) and aluminium chloride (70 g.) as in the case of the previous keto-acids. The semisolid keto-acid was dissolved in rectified spirit and allowed to stand when a crystalline solid separated, which after recrystallisation from hexane melted at 113° , yield 12 g. (Found: C, 74.32; H, 8.30. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 74.45; H, 8.02%).

The ethanolic mother liquor, obtained from above, was evaporated to leave a viscous residue. It was kept in a vacuum desiccator for a few days; no solid separated. It was purified by distillation as a heavy viscous mass, b.p. 200-205°/1 mm. It is a stereoisomer of the above keto-acid. It did not solidify; yield 20 g. (Found: C, 74.26; H, 8.14. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 74.45; H, 8.02%).

ββ-(4'-Methylcyclohexane)-δ-phenylvaleric Acid (II: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$).—The foregoing viscous liquid butyric acid (17 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (75 g.) and HCl (conc., 75 ml) for 36 hours. The reduced acid had b.p. 183-85°/1 mm, yield 10 g. (Found: C, 78.32; H, 9.41. $C_{17}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 78.46; H, 9.23%).

3-Methyl-8,9-benzo-10-keto-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (III: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$).—The above valeric acid (10 g.) was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid (P_2O_5 , 30 g., 89% H_3PO_4 , 15 ml). It is a light straw-coloured liquid, b.p. 162-63°/1 mm, yield 6.5 g. (Found: C, 84.36; H, 9.2. $C_{17}H_{22}O$ requires C, 84.29; H, 9.09%).

The 2,4-DNP of the spiro-ketone was crystallised from ethyl acetate as reddish orange crystals, m.p. 218-19°. (Found: C, 65.24; H, 6.27. $C_{23}H_{26}O_4N_4$ requires C, 65.40; H, 6.16%).

The crystalline solid isomer of the keto-acid (I: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$) was reduced by zinc amalgam and hydrochloric acid. The reduced acid was cyclised by polyphosphoric acid when a spiro-ketone, identical with (III: $R_1=H$, $R_2=Me$), boiling at 162-63°/1 mm, was obtained.

3-Methyl-8,9-benzo-spiro-(6,5)dodecane (IV: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$).—The spiro-ketone (III: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$) (10 g.) was reduced by gently boiling with amalgamated zinc (40 g.) and HCl (conc., 40 ml) for 24 hours. It is a colorless oil, b.p. 150-51°/1 mm, yield 5.9 g.; d_{20}^{20} 1.4298, n_D^{20} 1.5410, $[R_1]_D$ 70.72 (calc. 72.90). (Found: C, 89.26; H, 10.64. $C_{17}H_{24}$ requires C, 89.47; H, 10.52%).

Catalytic Dehydrogenation of the Spiro-hydrocarbon (IV: $R_1=H$; $R_2=Me$).—The spiro-hydrocarbon (2.7 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.29 g.) in a sealed tube at 380-400° for 16 hours. The product was subjected to chromatographic fractionation on Brockmann alumina with hexane as in the previous case. The first, second, and third eluates contained oily residues with odour like xylene after removal of the solvent. The oily residues were mixed and distilled, b.p. 145° (ca.). It was oxidised by an alkaline permanganate solution. An acid was isolated and identified as phthalic acid.

Each of the fourth, fifth, and sixth eluates contained oil with very little quantity of solid on removal of the solvent. The subsequent eluates contained no solute. The residues from the above eluates were separately converted into trinitrobenzene derivative. They melted in the range between 148° and 155°. The T.N.B. derivatives were mixed and crystallised repeatedly from rectified spirit when orange needles melting at 155° were obtained. The mixed melting point with the T.N.B. derivative of an authentic sample of 3-methylphenanthrene was not depressed. (Found: C, 62.54; H, 3.53. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{15}O_6N_3$: C, 61.22; H, 3.70%).

The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the T.N.B. derivative and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 62-63°. The mixed melting point with an authentic sample of 3-methylphenathrene remained unaltered. (Found: C, 93.62; H, 6.42. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{10}$: C, 93.75; H, 6.25%).

The picrate, prepared from the purified hydrocarbon, was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 40-141°. (Found: C, 59.65; H, 3.67. $C_{21}H_{15}O_7N_3$ requires C, 59.85; H, 3.56%).

RAMKRISHNA MISSION VIDYAMANDIR,
BELUR MATH, BELUR
AND
KRISHNAGAR GOVERNMENT COLLEGE,
KRISHNAGAR, WEST BENGAL.

Received July 16, 1962.